

The Impact of Using Digital Wallets on Generation Z's Consumptive Behavior

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A B S T R A C T

Digital wallets (*e-wallets*) are digital financial products that are considered a more efficient alternative to payments cash. Electronic money is usually stored in digital wallets to make transactions easier. Today's digital wallets provide benefits, convenience and efficiency in payment transactions, making it easier for generation Z to spend their money, thereby influencing their consumer behavior as well. Research shows that digital wallets have a significant impact on generation Z consumer behavior. Digital wallets are convenient, safe, efficient and innovative for generation Z retail transactions, especially in online deliveries, grocery orders and *e-commerce transactions*.

INTRODUCTION

The development of the global economy in both developed and developing countries cannot be separated from the role of money. (Trudel, 2019). Money plays the most important role in all areas of the economy including production, distribution and consumption (Chi Ying & Ismail Pakir Mohamed, 2021). Money is believed to be able to stimulate economic activity and facilitate the steps that individuals need to take to obtain goods and services that can meet their daily needs (Durante & Griskevicius, 2016).

The use of money as a medium of exchange emerged gradually over a very long period of time, until people began to use metal and paper as a means of transaction (Nhan PHAN et al., 2020). Rapid advances in information technology increase efficiency and reduce transaction time and costs (Gupta et al., 2022). Therefore, there is a tendency, especially among generation Z, to using a digital wallet or electronic money (*e-wallet*) for shopping, transportation, accommodation, meals, cinema tickets, tolls, electricity, water, telephone, etc (R. Kanhekar & N. Mane, 2015).

Supermarkets, minimarkets and even food stalls have started to offer electronic payment facilities (Chauhan, 2017) Menurut Jia et al., (2020). With the emergence of electronic money, the methods and proportions of metal and paper currency transactions are increasingly changing. Electronic money payments reduce cash circulation. On the other hand, the amount of electronic money in circulation is increasing (Nishibe, 2020). Digital wallets are not only easy to use and carry, but also provide enormous benefits for human survival (Tang et al., 2019).

For millions of people around the world, digital wallets are replacing cash and credit cards (Nainggolan et al., 2023). Do & Do (2020), Cash is the most common payment method used by students, followed by mobile banking and credit cards. Lee et al., (2023), states that interactivity and subjective norms influence every pleasure and satisfaction in using *e-wallet*. Perceived risk has no significant effect on *e-wallet enjoyment and satisfaction*, while visual attractiveness has a positive effect on perceived enjoyment but has no effect on satisfaction. In addition, enjoyment of using *e-wallets* is known to have a positive influence on impulse purchases, but satisfaction with *e-wallets* does not appear to have a significant relationship with impulse purchases. Besides that, Król and Zdonek, (2023) found that social influence had a significant positive effect on the intention to use a digital wallet, perceived ease of use had a significant positive effect on the intention to use a digital wallet, and perceived security also had a significant positive effect. This was found to have a significant positive influence on the intention to use digital wallets. (Sun & Xing, 2022). The use of digital wallets can stop or reduce students' consumption behavior (C. C. Lee & Chang, 2013). This means that students use e-money only when necessary, such as paying school fees or buying other basic necessities, according to research (Ramkumar, 2018) dan (Shin et al., 2022).

Studies Nguyen & Nguyen (2022) indicates that payment service providers want to encourage consumers to use *e-wallet services* to improve consumer behavior. Results obtained Ilieva et al., (2023) dan Subaramaniam et

al., (2020) provide specific recommendations for stakeholders in the payment processing value chain. Financial regulatory authorities can use the presented results when planning the development of payment systems. *E-wallet* marketers can use the proposed methodology to evaluate, compare and select alternative payment methods for their orders. E-wallet service providers can build robust multi-criteria systems to assess digital wallet adoption (G. Singh, 2019). By implementing the core value components of e-wallets, managers can manage and monitor payment platforms more efficiently and improve customer experience, thereby increasing the company's competitiveness (Zulni & Achiria, 2020). Findings Singh et al., (2017) dan Uduji et al., (2019) shows that there is a strong relationship between customer perceptions, preferences and satisfaction of mobile wallet users. The results also show that the use of digital wallets can influence people's consumption behavior in India (May et al., 2021). Based on the title above and various descriptions, digital wallets make it easier for people to carry out various transactions and have a significant impact on Gen Z consumer behavior. The purpose of this research is to raise the question of how much influence the use of digital wallets has on people's consumer behavior, especially Generation Z, and whether digital wallets have a positive impact?

METHODOLOGY

The type of research used is qualitative descriptive research, namely research that describes the variables that influence and the relationships between these variables to achieve research objectives. Qualitative data is collected in natural or real environments (Papillouda & Haeslerb, 2014). This research uses a descriptive research design. Descriptive research is research used to determine the value of one or more (independent) variables without comparing or connecting them with other variables (Uduji & Okolo-Obasi, 2018). Descriptive research can also be used to answer general questions (O'Dwyer, 2019). This is done in several stages: data collection, classification and analysis, drawing conclusions and writing a report with the main aim of creating an objective situation in describing the situation (To & Trinh, 2021). Therefore, researchers describe or explain the data obtained regarding Generation Z's use of digital wallets for transactions.

Population is a general field that includes subjects/objects with certain qualities and characteristics that are studied and determined by researchers and then draw conclusions (Rathore, 2016). The target of this research is the entire young generation who live in Makassar City and are generation Z digital wallet users. The target group for this research is the entire z generation Gen Z digital wallet users who live in the city of Makassar. Bara (2013) reveals that patterns are part of the quantities and characteristics that exist in a population. The sampling method used is *non-probability sampling*. This means that each member of the population does not have the same opportunity to be selected as a sample (Upadhyay et al., 2020). The sample population for this study was 30 people with normal distribution and were generation Z digital wallet users.

The data collection method in this research regarding the use of digital wallets is by using library and literature knowledge Easier & Index (2012) and

interview. The research analysis method uses descriptive analysis methods, especially non-statistical analysis methods which are suitable for non-quantitative text data (Zikhali, 2022). The data obtained is presented in the form of a qualitative description. As quoted by Pachpande & Kamble (2018), "Qualitative techniques are methods used to analyze data through written descriptions of data that describe them in detail and in detail according to phenomena that exist in reality (Sikri et al., 2019). In analyzing this data, the research team used the following method:

- 1) Inductive method, this method aims to draw conclusions based on certain statements or facts and finally draw general conclusions (Thomas et al., 2016). Therefore Karim et al., (2022) assesses that general generalizations can be drawn from many specific and specific facts or events.
- 2) Deductive method, namely drawing conclusions from confirmation of various general facts related to specific and specific problems (Su et al., 2023). Therefore, we can make clear generalizations from specific and general facts (Wu et al., 2022).
- 3) The comparative method is a method of completing the desired explanation by combining existing facts based on existing theories (Vatsa et al., 2023).

index in this research is research that has the main objective of using digital wallets for retail transactions through qualitative descriptive methods as well as interview and survey methods used in this research project. It is hoped that it can set standards for the use of digital wallets by generation Z. The main reason for conducting research This qualitative descriptive study aims to find out whether the use of digital wallets has an impact on generation Z consumer behavior. This research is expected to improve and develop Generation Z so they can live and control their spending and saving habits so they can manage their finances well.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

With digital wallet providers regularly offering discounts and cashback promotions, generation Z is realizing their heavy reliance on digital wallets for various transactions. Getting cashback of at least 20% or a 10% discount from sellers can encourage them to use their digital wallet for transactions (Chong et al., 2023).

Figure 1. Example of DANA Promo

Figure 2. Example of ShopeePay Promo

According to Zhipeng (2022) the analysis conducted, it shows that the use of cryptocurrencies in digital wallets has a significant impact on the behavior of generation Z consumers regarding the use of cash. This is clearly seen through the results obtained that 85-4% of respondent admitted to shopping cashless, 26.6% of respondents only used DANA as a digital wallet, and 12.0% of respondents trusted ShopeePay as their digital wallet, and 66.5% admitted to using two digital wallets simultaneously. ShopeePay is more popular by 71.8% of respondents compared to DANA which is only used by 28.2% of respondents. The reason is because ShopeePay holds discount or refund promotions more often than its competitor DANA.

Almost all respondents agreed that using a digital wallet helped them a lot in carrying out digital financial transactions (Sutticherchart & Rakthin, 2023). As many as 81.3% of respondents admitted to using digital wallets to buy or order food and drinks online, while 58.8% of respondents said they used digital wallets to buy electricity, PDAM, etc. At the same time, 18.8% of respondents said they used digital wallets to pay for parking and buy clothes, and 16.3% of respondents said they used them to buy other items in the family. The fact that 7 0% of those surveyed are high-level consumers and still want to use digital wallets is important because digital wallet providers have established very attractive partnerships with large retailers that are popular among teenagers.

The results of all research conducted to date show that generation Z cannot be separated from using digital wallets for all their needs (Jokić et al., 2019).

Promotions held by digital wallet providers in Indonesia always encourage generation Z to make online transactions. Poh Kiong et al. (2022) stated that generation Z, the busiest generation, seeks convenience in transactions. Compared to the DANA digital wallet, ShopeePay is much more popular because it has a wider range of applications, meeting the different needs of Generation Z in online financial transactions. Therefore, this research shows that Generation Z's consumer behavior increases along with the availability of digital wallets (Chen, 2017).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Research has shown that the use of electronic money in digital wallets has a significant impact on the consumer behavior of generation Z. Digital wallets are a simpler, safer and more efficient way to make cashless payments. The innovation makes it easier for generation Z to spend money, especially for retail transactions: online delivery, ordering groceries from partner suppliers, and e-commerce (Agárdi & Alt, 2022). Gen Z digital wallet users must make a reasonable distinction between their needs and wants to prevent consumer behavior and prioritize those needs using a prioritization scale when making transactions (Thuy et al., 2021).

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations so further research needs to be done on this topic "The Impact of Using Digital Wallets on Generation Z's Consumptive Behavior".

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